

PERFORMANCE EVALUATION OF CORN LEAVES DISEASES CLASSIFICATION USING LIGHTWEIGHT DEEP LEARNING

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ABSTRACT

Based on this research we proposed the suitable preprocessing method and changing activation layer in ShuffleNet model for corn leaves disease classification. This starts from preprocessing images which enhance contrast and denoise image to show the better method to be used in deep learning models. Then we also change the ReLU layer into ClippedReLU layer which works better in MobileNet-V2 to improve the better performance on ShuffleNet. The dataset used in this research is from Plant Village Dataset in Kaggle database. The result showed that contrast enhancement could improve the performance of deep learning models compared to denoise and original images. Also, the ShuffleNet + ClippedReLU layer improves some of the training parameters including time but not the accuracy. This changing activation layer on ShuffleNet needs more exploration to improve the accuracy.

Keywords: Corn leaves disease, preprocessing, enhance contrast, denoise, ClippedReLU, ShuffleNet, MobileNetV2

INTRODUCTION

Corn plant, or *Zea Mays* in scientific name, is one of the most important carbohydrate-producing food crops in the world. For residents of Central and South America, corn is a staple food, as is for some people in Africa and some parts of Indonesia. As we all know, Indonesia and China are the biggest corn-producing countries. At the present, corn has also become an important component of animal feed. Besides, various corn derivative products are used as raw materials for various pharmaceutical, cosmetic, and chemical industrial products.

Attention to the availability of complete, accurate, and up-to-date agricultural sector data is needed as a reference for the government and stakeholders in planning and policy formulation. Corn plants can also be affected by several diseases, including pests and planthoppers, etc. If the crop is infected by diseases, then the income of farmers will decrease.

Diagnosing plant diseases through optical observation of plant leaf symptoms has a very high degree of complexity. Due to this complexity, the large number of cultivated plants and their phytopathological problems, even experienced agronomists and plant pathologists often fail to successfully diagnose specific diseases, leading to wrong conclusions and treatments. The existence of automatic computing systems for detecting and diagnosing plant diseases will provide valuable assistance to agronomists who are required to make such diagnoses through optical observation of the leaves of infected plants. If the system is easy to use and easily accessible through a simple mobile application, it may also be a valuable tool for farmers in the world who lack the proper infrastructure to provide agronomic and phytopathological advice [1][2].

According to some of the research papers, new and modified Deep Learning architectures have been introduced to obtain better/transparent detection of plant disease. Such as in [3], eight different plant diseases were recognized by three classifiers, Support Vector Machines (SVM), Extreme Learning Machine (ELM), and K-Nearest Neighbour (KNN), used with the state-of-the-art deep learning models like GoogLeNet-V2, ResNet-50, ResNet-101, Inception-V3, InceptionResNet-V2, and SqueezeNet. A comparison was made between those models, and ResNet-50 with SVM classifier got the best results in

terms of performance metrics like sensitivity, specificity, and F1-score. In [4], a new deep learning model was introduced to obtain more accurate detection of plant diseases as compared to SVM, AlexNet, GoogLeNet, ResNet-20, and VGG-16 models. This model achieved 97.62% accuracy for classifying apple plant diseases. Moreover, the data set extended in 13 different ways. The whole data set was transformed into Gaussian noise and PCA jittering as well. In [5], specific CNN architectures were trained and assessed, to form an automated plant disease detection and diagnosis system, based on simple images of leaves of healthy and diseased plants. The available dataset contained images captured in both experimental (laboratory) setups and real cultivation conditions in the field.

CNN architecture are also applied to corn plant disease classification. Some of CNN models such as VGG, DenseNet, InceptionV3, MobileNet, AlexNet, EfficientNet Modify CNN ResNet, SqueezeNet, GoogleNet. All these researches have been collected by [6]. The results showed that CNN models are powerful to detect corn image diseases. Yet all the CNN models still need improvement to reach maximal accuracy. By the related works, we want to improve the power of classification using lightweight CNN. We will compare the performance between ShuffleNet and MobileNet-V2 and also modified activation layer of ShuffleNet, based on denoising and enhancement image. In the context of image classification, preprocessing include denoising and contrast enhancement are methods for improve the classification [7][8]. By reducing noise and enhancing contrast, the preprocessed images can provide more useful information to the classification model, leading to improved performance. Another classification improvement we use is changing activation layer in ShuffleNet models. We will change the original ReLU layer in ShuffleNet to ClippedReLU, the variation of ReLU which also used in MobileNet-V2 (ReLU6). This changing is to obtain the performance of ShuffleNet using another activation layer, which showed better on MobileNet-V2.

METHODS

This chapter define the research flow to obtain the best model in classify corn leaves disease. The research starts from collecting data which contain three kinds of disease and healthy leaves. The collected data is 4,173 images which used to train and to test the models. Then the data was pre-processed using two filter images, to enhance and denoise the image before classification process. After all preprocessing was done, the dataset were trained by ShuffleNet and MobileNet-V2. All the results were compared to choose the best models between them which provide best accuracy.

Fig. 1 Research Flow.

Dataset Collection

Plant leaf diseases images are part of the natural images. It was a little bit complex and has many difficulties. This dataset has some features and advantages. The other reason, it has different object sizes for each class, whereas the same class has different sizes and appearances at the same time, as shown in Table 1. All this serves the study's aim, which is to create a model that can manage all these differences and challenges. The dataset for this study was taken from Kaggle database from Plant Village dataset [9].

Table 1. Number of Datasets

Class	Number of Images	Sample of Image
Healthy	1,162	
Common Rust	1,192	
Cercospora	834	
Northern Leaf Blight	985	
TOTAL	4,173	

The used dataset is corn leaves images, which are divided into four classes, Common Rust, Healthy, Cercospora and also Northern Leaf Blight. The total number of datasets used is 4,173 images, with Common rust 1,192, Healthy 1,162, Cercospora 834, and Northern leaf blight 985. The dataset was separated for training and testing, with the total 80% for training and 20% for testing.

Preprocessing Dataset

Preprocessing method plays a very important role in image classification techniques and applications. For optimal computer vision outcomes, attention to image preprocessing is required so it could improve image features by eliminating unwanted features. Preprocessing aims to reduce the data size, find the relation between data, normalize data, remove outliers and extract features for data [10]. In this research, we will separate two methods of preprocessing, denoising image and contrast enhancement. These preprocessing techniques have been implemented in Matlab and present the results of experiments on real data. The preprocessing result have been applied to the training data and testing data.

Denoising Image

The method used for this denoising is Wavelet Transform. This will apply to all of the training and testing images. We used a wavelet variable that uses a Bi-orthogonal wavelet with 5 vanishing levels and 3 reconstruction levels. Afterward, wavelet decomposition applied after converting the noisy image to bi-orthogonal wavelet domain and get the decomposition vector. It also apply soft and hard thresholding. Given a resolution of analysis, the image denoising process is adaptive (i.e. does not require further parameter adjustment), and the selection of a gain factor provides the desired detail enhancement. The distribution of detail coefficients is modelled by a composition of Gaussian and Generalized Laplacian probability density functions at each scale, a Shrinkage function is assembled. Such shrinkage functions

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are combined in consecutive levels to preserve edges that are persistent over scales and remove residual noise [11]. Finally, an adaptive piecewise linear enhancement function is applied to the denoised wavelet coefficients. Figure 2 below shows the sample of denoising image.

Fig. 2 Sample of dataset (A) Before denoising image. (B) After denoising image.

Enhance Image

It is most expedient to use homomorphic processing of the original image to enhance them. Such processing, in addition to increasing the image contrast, eliminates the uneven illumination of the observed surface. We applied the fourier transformation in the image using Matlab. The second step is setting Gaussian high-pass filter in images. Then we generate mask to apply the Gaussian Homomorphic Filtering, according to the distance from center with formula 1, where h is height and w is weight:

$$D = \sqrt{\left(\frac{i-h}{2}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{j-w}{2}\right)^2} \quad (1)$$

Fig. 3 Sample of dataset (A) Before contrast enhancement image. (B) After contrast enhancement image. Contrast enhancement methods made image features more distinct, but its amplification in the feature quality was not that significant. The image enhancement using FFT and Gaussian filtering algorithm achieves the purpose of preprocessing by adjusting the color, and the illumination invariant feature algorithm achieves the purpose of preprocessing by extracting the features of the images. All of the datasets that have been preprocessed with denoising image and contrast enhancement image in this step will be used in classification.

Classification

This stage is to classify the images of the plant corn leaf disease. The images which used in the research are the original images and the preprocessed image. The image size is resized to 224×224 pixels. These images are used in the training and testing process in each model during classification. Image classification is done using CNN with three different models. The parameter has the same setting on all models.

Fig. 4 Image Classification Process.

The Figure 4 above showed the process of classification in this research. This start from input image which has three types of images. The three types are Original Image, Denoise Image, and Enhance Image. These images will be classified to three models of Deep Learning. The models are ShuffleNet, MobileNet-V2, and ShuffleNet with replaced activation layer. All the models will learn features from image to find its class among four. The classes are Healthy, Cercospora, Norhtern Leaf Blight, and Common Rust.

Shufflenet

The architecture of ShuffleNet model consists of blocks which has *Convolutional Layer Group*, *Channel Shuffle*, *DepthWise Convolutional*, which continued by a *ReLU* as an activation layer [12]. Channel Shuffle has been introduced in ShuffleNet model, and become of the success in some researches, including image classification task. ShuffleNet could classify 1000 classes and in this research it only needs four classes. In addition, ShuffleNet has fewer learning parameters than MobileNet-V2 but has almost the same accuracy in classification task [12][13]. It could process large datasets with high accuracy as MobileNet-V2. The classification start from three kind of input images, continued by ShuffleNet in training and testing. Afterwards, training and testing result are compared to other models

Fig. 5 Layers in ShuffleNet Architecture [14].

MobileNet-V2

Such as ShuffleNet, MobileNet-V2 is also the lightweight models on CNN. MobileNet had been introduced for mobile and embedded vision applications in [15], which is based on depthwise separable convolutions. MobileNet-V2 is designed to be small and efficient, with fewer parameters than MobileNet (V1). This one is good choice for apps development where memory and storage space are limited, such as on mobile devices. MobileNet-V2 is still able to achieve high levels of accuracy in image classification and other computer vision tasks. In fact, it outperforms many other small neural networks in terms of accuracy. The structure of MobileNet-V2 contain some layers like convolutional 1 x 1, depthwise 3 x 3 followed by ReLU layer, and repeat for some blocks to learn the feature in images.

Fig. 6 The basic architecture of MobileNet-V2: (Block_1) MobileNetV2 units with stride = 2, (Block_2) MobileNetV2 units with stride = 1 [16].

ShuffleNet – Changing Activation Layer

ShuffleNet has ReLU layer as the activation function layer to bring out the important features. ReLU, which stands for Rectified Linear Unit, is a commonly used activation function in neural networks. In ShuffleNet, the ReLU activation function is applied after each convolution operation. The ReLU activation function sets any negative values in the output of the convolution operation to zero, which helps to avoid the vanishing gradient problem and speeds up the training process [17]. Overall, using ReLU activation in ShuffleNet can improve the performance of the model by introducing nonlinearity and enabling the learning of more complex features.

Clipped ReLU, on the other hand, is a variation of ReLU that addresses the "dying ReLU" problem by limiting the output of the activation function to a certain range. In other words, if the output is less than zero, it is set to zero, but if it is greater than a certain value (often 6), it is clipped to that value. This prevents neurons from becoming permanently inactive and can lead to improved performance. By this explanation, we tried to change the ReLU to Clipped ReLU in activation function layer in ShuffleNet. We will obtain the performance accuracy using Clipped ReLU. Another modified on ShuffleNet layer have been done in [18] which reduce the layer and resulted better than original model.

Fig. 7 (a) Modified activation layer ShuffleNet using Clipped ReLU; (b) Original ShuffleNet with ReLU as activation layer.

Result Analysis

The process of detecting plan leaf diseases which is carried out by classification using CNN is analyzed with several parameters to be seen. This is needed to see the results of the original images and preprocessing images for the *training* and *testing* process. These parameters include *accuracy*, *recall*, and *precision*, and *f-measure* by using this formula [19].

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \quad (2)$$

$$Recall = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad (3)$$

$$Accuracy = \frac{TP+TN}{TP+TN+FP+FN} \quad (4)$$

$$F - Measure = 2 \times \frac{(Recall) \times (Precision)}{Recall + Precision} \quad (5)$$

Based on equations 2 till 5, the accuracy value is to determine the percentage of the model to classify all images, where True Positive (TP) is the number of correctly identified testing as positive. True Negative (TN) is the number of correctly testing image which is identified as negative. False Positive (FP) is positive image classified as negative, and False Negative (FN) is a negative image that is classified as positive. Accuracy is used to measure system performance on CNN models to classify all images. Comparisons of these parameters is needed to compare models that are lighter but still produce maximum accuracy. This comparison is needed to be one aspect that shows a more efficient model comparison. It also comparing the training result from training process in each models.

RESULTS

After training process, the time, loss, and training accuracy are obtained. Also in testing, the accuracy, precision, recall, and f-measure from each models have been obtained. For three models there are three kind of dataset which are original image, denoising image, and contrast enhancement image. The results from three kinds of deep learning models are shown in table.

Table 2. The results from three kinds of deep learning models

Training	Model	Original Image	Denoising Image	Contrast Enhancement Image
Time	ShuffleNet	15 m 41 s	12 m 57 s	12 m 50 s
	Mobilenet-V2	21 m 45 s	15 m 39 s	15 m 30 s
	ShuffleNet + ClippedReLU	12 m 37 s	12 m 30 s	12 m 3 s
Loss Training	ShuffleNet	0.24	0.32	0.25
	Mobilenet-V2	0.20	0.24	0.19
	ShuffleNet + ClippedReLU	0.19	0.19	0.22
Training Accuracy	ShuffleNet	93.29	91.55	93.33
	Mobilenet-V2	93.16	91.32	93.56
	ShuffleNet + ClippedReLU	92.77	92.85	91.90

Table 2 above showed the training results from deep learning models. There was three parameters of training we collected. The first parameter is time training to obtain the time of training process in each deep learning models. The result from MobileNet-V2 reached the longest time to train. The ShuffleNet + ClippedReLU reached faster time in all datasets compared to original ShuffleNet model.

The Loss Training obtained from three models, reached the highest up to 0.32 on denoising image in ShuffleNet model. On MobileNet-V2 it obtained lower score in loss. And table 3 showed ShuffleNet+ClippedReLU obtained the lowest loss training in each datasets.

For training accuracy, the MobileNet-V2 in contrast enhancement up to 93.56. It decreased on original and denoising images. ShuffleNet reached the highest on contrast enhancement with 93.33. The contrast enhancement on ShuffleNet + ClippedReLU reached the lowest score with 91.90 training accuracy. But it show better training accuracy with 92.85 rather than two other models.

Table 3. The testing results from three kinds of deep learning models

Models	Recall (%)			Precision(%)			F-Measure(%)		
	Original	Denois e	Enhanc e	Origina l	Denois e	Enhanc e	Original	Denois e	Enhanc e
ShuffleNet	96,8	97,6	97,6	97	97	98	96	97	97
MobileNet-V2	98	96	98	98	97	98	98	96	98
ShuffleNet + ClippedReLU	95	95	97	95	95	96	95	95	96,5

Table 4. The accuracy from three kinds of deep learning models

Models	Accuracy		
	Original Image	Denoising Image	Contrast Enhancement
ShuffleNet	96.8%	97.6%	97.6%
MobileNet-V2	98.4%	97.5%	98.8%
ShuffleNet+ClippedReLU	96.1%	95.7%	96.1%

The table 4 above showed that the best model to recognize the four classes in corn leaf disease is MobileNet-V2 using contrast enhancement image. MobileNet-V2 reached original image with 98,4% and denoising image with 97,5% accuracy. The model obtains up to 98.8% accuracy in classification corn leaf. The contrast enhancement image showed better result than original and denoising images. ShuffleNet showed the result in contrast enhancement and denoising image perform better than original image with 97,6% accuracy. ShuffleNet-ClippedReLU performs better on both enhancement and original image, decrease in denoising image. It shows that ShuffleNet-ClippedReLU could not classify better than using original embedded activation function layer, ReLU. Although the result not high as the original model ShuffleNet, but it still reach the high score of accuracy up to 96,1%. Some parameters or environment in layer ShuffleNet may not suitable for ClippedReLU layer and cause the degradation of accuracy from original ShuffleNet.

CONCLUSION

Based on result analysis, this research obtained some conclusion. MobileNet-V2 model is the best of three models which have tested to classify corn plant diseases into four classes. Furthermore, it is proved that preprocessing method which is enhance contrast could improve the performance of deep learning. It shown by the higher score of accuracy in enhance contrast image rather than original image. But the using the denoising image could decrease the accuracy of deep learning. Another obtained result is accuracy from modified ShuffleNet-ClippedReLU. This showed that using ClippedReLU did not improve

the accuracy on model of ShuffleNet. But it still showed the high score to the corn diseases classification task. It also shows better result in training process compared to original ShuffleNet model. This could be caused by some problems, also ClippedReLU has need more exploration to change and to adapt in ShuffleNet architecture.

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